

REFORMS IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND THEIR IMPACT ON SOCIETY.

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information on the reforms in the field of culture and art in our country and their impact on the life of society, how teachers working in secondary schools create opportunities for students to identify and realize their talents.

Keywords: reform, culture, art, music, interest, student, skill, society, melody, performing arts school, education, decision.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada mamlakatimizdagi madaniyat va san'at sohasidagi islohotlar va ularning jamiyat hayotiga ta'siri, umumta'lim maktablarida faoliyat ko'rsatayotgan o'qituvchi - pedagoglar tomonidan o'quvchilarni iste'dodini aniqlash va ro'yobga chiqarishda qanday vazifalarni amalga oshirishlari uchun imkoniyatlar yaratish haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: islohot, madaniyat, san'at, musiqa, qiziqish, o'quvchi, mahorat, jamiyat, kuy, ijrochilik maktabi, ta'lim, qaror.

Аннотация: В статье дается подробная информация о реформах в сфере культуры и искусства в нашей стране и их влиянии на общественную жизнь, а также о создании возможностей для учителей, работающих в средних школах, выявлять и реализовывать таланты учащихся.

Ключевые слова: реформа, культура, искусство, музыка, интерес, ученик, мастерство, общество, мелодия, школа исполнительских искусств, образование, решение.

Among the many factors of upbringing in the development of the young generation, music occupies a special place. Music, with its unique nature, has the power to greatly influence the spiritual world of young people. It is no secret to any of us today that under the influence of music, melody and harmony, a person's emotional world grows, perception and thinking are formed, the desire for goodness, love of beauty, the desire to preserve mother nature, and serve for the prosperity of the beloved homeland are growing.

Today, young men and women who have taken their first steps on the path of art are diligently studying the secrets of musical art. As is known, music clubs and music lessons are held in all educational institutions of our republic, along with various disciplines. In addition, it is necessary to check the octave of some

frets in each string.[1] Participation in music clubs is undoubtedly a great performing school for young musicians.

The state program for the implementation of the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for the period of 2022-2026 in the “Year of honoring human dignity and active neighborhood” on additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art.[2] The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 112 of February 2, 2022 “On additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art”, the introduction of state educational standards, places great responsibility on teachers of music culture. Among the many factors of education, music has a special place in leading the young generation to maturity. Music, with its unique nature, has the power to greatly influence the spiritual world of young people.[3] As indicated in the state educational standard, special importance is attached to the Uzbek national musical art in music culture classes, a wide place is given to performing songs from spiritual education ceremonies, which are one of the folk traditions of local-style directions, and singing and listening to allas, lapars and yallas created in the folk way.

The Resolution of our esteemed President Shavkat Mirziyoev “On measures to improve the activity of musical art” is both a source of pride and joy for us. The younger generation, who are happy about this, and the teachers who mentor them, will have even more opportunities, and will benefit from their work. Songs that encourage children to love nature, respect adults, and work hard can serve as the basis for each song studied in music culture lessons, or in other words, in educational institutions, it is possible to educate young people on the basis of the activities of extracurricular music clubs and by linking the content of the songs taught in them with the above qualities.

The purpose of music clubs is to organize students’ free time on a voluntary basis, while strengthening their abilities, forming aesthetic taste, and expanding their spiritual worldview. The principles that form the worldview of the choral culture are especially important today, when universal spiritual values are being revived.[4] It is not for nothing that our President said: “The dream of a new Uzbekistan, in relation to our days, is the ideological and spiritual foundation that determines the requirements of the times, its true nature, driving forces and factors, the creative zeal inherent in our people, and a clear expression of our large-scale reforms”. So, aesthetic education is the core of spirituality.

The main tasks of each teacher working in secondary schools are to provide students with knowledge during the training process, but also to organize musical and purposeful educational extracurricular activities. Music and singing activities have been of special importance in compositional creativity since ancient times.[5] The main objective of events held in educational institutions and the main task of their organizers (music teachers) is to organize them in a way that deeply understands our national values.

Events prepared and held in music clubs in the educational sphere are of particular importance. It is necessary to enrich the spiritual world of young students by entertaining them with entertaining, educational, and mass events that have become a tradition in our country. In general, educational institutions cannot be imagined without clubs. The teacher also examines each child's musical ability.[6]

By using songs specific to spiritual education in music circles, teachers and educators are able to form in the minds of students an understanding of the world, intellectual, moral, volitional and physical perfection. In short, through songs, performance becomes more diverse, and the effectiveness of training increases.

Therefore, if the work carried out in educational institutions is properly organized, in particular, if serious shortcomings are not allowed in planning the distribution of training, the effectiveness of training will continue to increase.

In music circles, students develop their musical abilities, acquire the skills of singing, playing musical instruments, and dancing, while in folklore music circles, they study ancient customs, traditions, various sayings, riddles, and proverbs left by our ancestors, and learn songs from national folk spiritual education ceremonies. In conclusion, in the development of the activities of circles in educational institutions, music circles attract the attention of children with their uniqueness and direction.

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